

SITE GPR	YEAR 11	AREA B	SECTOR	ELEVATION Min: <i>not shot in</i> Max:	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 1463 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropic		
In cross-section? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No			In elevation drawing? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No		Photos: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No #: 2012-2018	Photo Model: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No #: 309	
DEFINITION <i>Soil within imbrex burial</i>				Covered by <input type="checkbox"/> SU:	Fills <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SU: 1392	Filled by <input type="checkbox"/> SU:	
HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? <input type="checkbox"/> Color <input type="checkbox"/> Composition <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Compaction			FORMATION PROCESS <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Accumulation <input type="checkbox"/> Construction <input type="checkbox"/> Cutting <input type="checkbox"/> Erosion <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse <input type="checkbox"/> Intentional deposition				
INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are					SOIL/MATRIX		
Anthropic		Geological		Organic		clay 15% silt 80% sand 5%	
<input type="checkbox"/> Pottery <input type="checkbox"/> Tiles <input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Glass		<input type="checkbox"/> Nails <input type="checkbox"/> Marble <input type="checkbox"/> Quarried debris <input type="checkbox"/> Slag <input type="checkbox"/> Brick <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt slabs <input type="checkbox"/> Opus signinum <input type="checkbox"/> Painted plaster <input type="checkbox"/> Burnt Adobe <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) <i>r</i> <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Charcoal <i>r</i> <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input type="checkbox"/> Animal bones <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Shells <i>m</i> <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	
					Compaction <input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input type="checkbox"/> Compact <input type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft		
					Color <input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)		
UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)							
Northern Limit		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit		Depth: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original			
Southern Limit		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit					
Western Limit		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit					
Eastern Limit		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit		NO OVERLEIGH			
STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE							
Is equal to:				Is bound to (only for masonry):			
Is abutted by:				Abuts: 1460			
Is covered by:				Covers:			
Is cut by:				Cuts:			
Is filled by:				Fills: 1392			
OBSERVATIONS							
soil inside imbrex tube of grave — excavated by trowel + brush, dry conditions							
DESCRIPTION							
Position within sector: <i>central, within N-S corridor</i>							
Shape: <i>conforms to shape of imbrex tube-coffin SU 1392</i>							
For layers complete this section:							
Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions): <i>no slope, soil accumulated within the U-shape of the imbrices</i>							
Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope): <i>three medium size tufo fragments at the southern end of fill</i>							
Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?): <i>homogenous</i>							
Nature of the interface with layer below: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> diffuse <input type="checkbox"/> commingled <input type="checkbox"/> other (specify)							
For cuts complete this section:				Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North):			
Cut edges: <input type="checkbox"/> rounded <input type="checkbox"/> straight							
Cut sides: <input type="checkbox"/> straight <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> convex <input type="checkbox"/> sloping							
Cut bottom: <input type="checkbox"/> flat <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> irregular							
How is cut top edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded							
How is cut bottom edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded							
Observations:							

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)
 Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

soil that was found within the imbrices which contained the skeleton. Skeleton showed signs of bioturbation.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No
 Total volume of layer (buckets): 1/2 bucket
 Sample quantity (buckets): 1/2 bucket
 Sample fraction (%): 100%

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No
 If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):
 Size:

SIEVING: Yes No
 Total volume of layer (buckets): 1/2
 Sample quantity (buckets): 1/2
 Sample fraction (%): 100%

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY
 Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by	T. Hart	on	27/7/11
Revised by	CHH	on	28.7.11
PDFd by	BCR	on	1/8/11
Entered by		on	